

Micromechanics and Reliability Based Composite Material Characterization for Wind Turbine Blade Composites

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a coupled approach for stiffness property prediction of composite materials used in wind turbine blades using advanced micromechanics and reliability-based methodologies. The coupled approach demonstrates how to map the uncertainties in the fiber and matrix properties onto the equivalent stiffness properties of unidirectional (UD) composite laminates. Compared to the traditional deterministic approach, the probabilistic method is a more reliable means to account for uncertainties, especially in the design of the most critical component of a wind turbine, the blades. Square (SQR) and hexagonal (HEX) unit cells were employed for the estimation of the composite equivalent properties. E-glass fiber and MY750 epoxy matrix are considered in this work. The results from numerical experimentation conform well with the available test data and to the results from the Modified Rule of Mixture (MROM). A probabilistic analysis using Monte Carlo Simulation with Latin Hypercube Sampling was used to assess the uncertainties in the equivalent properties according to the variability in the basic properties of the constituents. Furthermore, a sensitivity analysis based on the Spearman Rank Order correlation coefficients was carried out to highlight the influence of important properties of the constituents on the equivalent properties of the UD. As an illustration, the above mentioned micromechanics and probabilistic approach are applied to analyze a 5 MW wind turbine blade section under static loading. Results demonstrate the possibility of the coupled approach at macro level (structure) from micro level (unit cell) with the aim to design robust structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The size of wind turbines is increasing to capture more energy and this trend will continue into the future [1]. Several multi-MW prototype wind turbines exist for offshore applications [2-3]. The power of a wind turbine scales as square of the rotor diameter, while the mass of the blade (for similar conceptual designs) scales as the cube of rotor diameter. Considering these scaling laws one might predict that in the end material costs would govern and avert further scaling. The cost of the blade would then also scale as the cube of rotor diameter but advanced structural concepts reduce its scaling exponent to ~2.5 [4]. A polymer-based composite material is a good choice for large structures such as wind turbine blades. The high strength-to-density ratio, high stiffness-to-density ratio, good fracture toughness, fatigue performance and suitability for use in fast production of large structures makes composites a good choice for their use in structural applications. The composite properties provided by the manufacturer are generally the average properties in a particular manufacturing environment. On top of this, manufacturers usually don't mention the number of tests that they performed to obtain the average. This adds risk to structural design, especially for large-scale composite layups such as blades. It is impossible to completely control variation in the composite properties. There are many factors that contribute to that variation including: batch-to-batch production, manufacturing conditions like temperature, pressure, and humidity, curing time, labour skill, along with the property variations in the basic building blocks of the ply (the fiber and the matrix). These variations in the mechanical properties of composite materials are due primarily to variation in the properties of the constituents - the fiber and matrix [5]. This variation in properties establishes a scatter in the response of a structure made up from this material, for example, the deflection of the wind turbine blade. Therefore, it is

necessary to consider the variable nature of composite properties at the design stage. Current wind turbine blade design is based on a deterministic approach with a large factor of safety to ensure target static and fatigue limits [6]. It is very expensive experimentally to obtain the design allowables for a composite laminate in a deterministic approach as significant test campaigns for each candidate layup are required.

The micromechanics (MM) based homogenization approach is good alternative to characterize the stiffness properties of composite materials [7-8]. The Rule of Mixtures (ROM), also known as the Simple Rule of Mixture (SROM), is one of the oldest and simplest forms of micromechanics for calculating mechanical properties of unidirectional plies [7, 9-10]. Halpin [11] proposed a Modified Rule of Mixture (MROM) as there are shortcomings in calculating the transverse Young's modulus and in-plane shear modulus using SROM. Dong et al. [12] simulate the behaviour of various unit cells using an asymptotic homogenization technique. Other researchers have considered the uncertainty in the basic constituent's properties with the homogenization approach. Kamiński and Kleiber [13] calculated the first two probabilistic moments of the elasticity tensor using the homogenization method of composite structure. However, due to the complicated mathematical formulation, these studies are of limited applicability.

The present study aims at bringing together high fidelity micro-model based stiffness calculations of composite materials and probabilistic analysis. The homogenization approach coupled with a Monte Carlo simulation method is used to predict variability in composite material properties. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the concept of the Representative Unit Cell (RUC) models and the detailed stiffness properties calculation procedure using Rule of Mixture and homogenization based approaches. Section 3 provides details of the Monte Carlo Simulation along with Latin Hypercube sampling and sensitivity analysis. Section 4 presents the results. Section 5 details the applicability of the method to a wind turbine blade analysis. Section 6 summarizes the most important conclusions drawn from this study and highlights the topics require investigation in the future.

2 THEORY

2.1 Representative Unit Cell (RUC) Models

The wind turbine blade structure is made up of polymer-based composite laminates, which are in turn made up of plies stacked in a certain sequence. These plies are made up of fibre and matrix constituents. All these levels are divided into two main groups, the macro and micro levels as shown in Figure 1. The fibres are randomly arranged in the real unidirectional (UD) ply. The far left side of Figure 2 shows a cross section of a continuous UD ply [14]. There is no obvious regular pattern in which the fibres are arranged. A true representation of the fibre arrangement is shown in the middle of Figure 2. To aid computation, an idealized fibre arrangement is used, as shown in the far right side of the Figure 2. In this study, two idealized RUC models are used: square (SQR) RUC and hexagonal (HEX) RUC, as shown at the bottom of Figure 2. Other choices for the RUC, such as triangular RUC, could be exploring in the future.

Figure 1: Macro and Micro Levels

Figure 2: Representative Unit Cell Models

2.2 Rule of Mixture (ROM)

Structures made up from composite materials can be designed by tailoring the constituent properties. This requires high fidelity analysis and design of composite materials. Micromechanics is an approach that handles this scenario by establishing a relationship between the constituents and the ply or lamina. Several theoretical models have been proposed for the prediction of composite properties from those of the constituent fiber and matrix. An investigation of the existing micromechanics models has been summarized by Hashin [15]. The Rule of Mixtures (ROM) is one of the oldest and simplest forms of micromechanics for calculating the mechanical properties of unidirectional plies [7, 9-10]. There is not an accurate prediction for the transverse Young's modulus $E_{22,eq}$ and in-plane shear modulus $G_{12,eq}$ through SROM. This deficiency is overcome by the Modified Rule of Mixture (MROM) as proposed by Halpin [11].

2.3 Ply Stiffness Computational Procedure with RUC

It is not easy to determine experimentally the longitudinal and transverse shear moduli of unidirectional composites. It is also difficult to predict these moduli using MROM as they require ply level information [7]. Thus, numerical techniques such as the finite element method (FEM) are needed to facilitate these predictions. The stiffness properties of a unidirectional (UD) ply are calculated using FEM from the constituent's properties: the fibre and resin (or matrix) properties; fibre volume fraction V_f which controls the geometric parameter of the RUC. For example, in the case of SQR RUC, the radius of the unit cell is given as $r_f^{SQR} = \sqrt{V_f xy / \pi}$, where x and y is lengths of square unit cell.

The behaviour (stress and strain fields) of fiber and resin under uniform loading is quite different due to their different material properties. Therefore, special attention must be paid in order to make sure that linear stress-strain relationships can be used to compute the elastic properties of the lamina. In the stiffness properties prediction procedure, it is assumed that in an undamaged state both constituents are perfectly bonded everywhere along the length of the fibre/resin interface. For a fully reversible linear material domain, the constitutive relationship between stress and strain for a UD ply is given in Equation (1). For the plane stress case, the stiffness matrix \bar{C} is invertible to obtain a compliance matrix \bar{S} . Their product must produce a unity matrix, i.e. $[\bar{S}] = [\bar{C}]^{-1}$. By definition, ply stiffness properties can be computed from the elements of the $[\bar{S}]$ matrix [14].

$$\begin{pmatrix} \bar{\sigma}_1 \\ \bar{\sigma}_2 \\ \bar{\sigma}_3 \\ \bar{\sigma}_4 \\ \bar{\sigma}_5 \\ \bar{\sigma}_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{C}_{11} & \bar{C}_{12} & \bar{C}_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{C}_{21} & \bar{C}_{22} & \bar{C}_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{C}_{31} & \bar{C}_{32} & \bar{C}_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{C}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_1 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_2 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_3 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_4 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_5 \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_6 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

2.4 Boundary Conditions on RUC

The homogenization approach acts as a bridge between the microscopic and macroscopic scale analyses. Homogenization consists of two steps: 1) calculate local stresses and strains in constituents 2) use homogenization to obtain global stresses and strains for elastic property calculations. The successful implementation of homogenization assumes that the RUC has global repetition or periodicity. There are varieties of homogenization approaches to predict the composite material behaviour [9, 16]. The homogenization technique given by Sun and Vaidya [16] is the most widely used because of its relatively low computation cost and this can be achieved by applying proper boundary conditions (BCs) that are periodic. These periodic BCs give more practical results compared with other boundary conditions such as uniform stress boundary conditions or kinematic uniform boundary conditions, and have been validated by various researchers [17-18]. The periodic boundary conditions satisfy three conditions: 1) the deformation should be the same on the opposite surface; 2) the stress vectors acting on opposite surfaces should be opposite in direction in order to have stress continuity across the boundaries of unit cell; 3) there is no separation or overlap between the neighbouring RUC. The displacement field boundary condition on the boundary Γ of domain Ω of the unit cell is given in Equation (2) as stated by Suquet [19]:

$$u_i(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ik} x_k + u_i^*(x_1, x_2, x_3) \quad (2)$$

In the above, $\bar{\varepsilon}_{ik}$ is the global average strain of the periodic structure and x_k represents a linear distributed displacement field. u_i^* is a periodic part of the displacement from one RUC to another on the boundary surface and, unfortunately, it cannot be directly applied to the boundaries since it is unknown.

3 PROBABILISTIC ANALYSIS

3.1 Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) Approach and Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS)

Most probabilistic techniques require running deterministic models multiple times with different realizations of random input variables. The key difference between various probabilistic techniques is the choice of the realization from the current analysis to the previous one. A probabilistic analysis answers a number of questions: 1) how much scatter induced due to randomness in the input variables; 2) what is the probability the output parameters are no longer fulfilled based on design criterion; 3) which random input variable most affect the output parameters which helps to screen the design variables [20]?. The Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) approach is one of the most general tools to perform stochastic analysis under uncertainty of input variables [21]. In this work, the second order statistics of the responses are obtained using MCS with the random input variables (RVs) specified by their mean μ and standard deviation σ . The MCS consists of three steps: 1) generation of realization corresponding to probability distribution function (PDF) – Latin Hypercube Sampling is used for this purpose in this work; 2) a finite element simulation evaluates responses for each realization; 3) statistical analysis of the results yields valuable information concerning the sensitivities of the responses to the stochastic RVs. In the Latin Hypercube Sampling technique the range of all random

input variables is divided into n intervals with equal probability and the sample generation process has a memory in the meaning that the sampling points cannot cluster together.

3.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Analysis of parameter sensitivity investigates the effect of variability of certain input random variables on the variability of design-relevant response quantities; the sensitivities can be described by coefficients of correlation. The most commonly used coefficient of correlation proposed by Bravais-Pearson is given in Equation (3) between two random variables X and Y:

$$r_{X,Y} = \frac{Cov(X,Y)}{\sqrt{Var(X)}\sqrt{Var(Y)}} \quad (3)$$

The flow chart to calculate probabilistic properties of a UD composite based on the constituent's uncertainties in a modular fashion is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Probabilistic Analysis Flow Chart

4 RESULTS and DISCUSSION

4.1 Boundary Conditions for 2D Unit Cell

The periodic boundary conditions (BCs) devised by Xia [18] and given in Equation (4) are applied to a unit cell FEM model which insures that the composite has the same deformation mode and there is no separation between unit cells. To verify the BCs, a 2-dimensional unit cell model is considered first. The fiber volume fraction is 50%. The elastic moduli and Poisson's ratio for the fiber and matrix are $E_f = 72500 MPa$, $\nu_f = 0.22$ and $E_m = 2600 MPa$, $\nu_m = 0.42$, respectively.

$$u_i^{j+}(x, y, z) - u_i^{j-}(x, y, z) = c_i^j, (i, j = x, y, z) \quad (4)$$

A simple fibre-matrix domain was defined in the ANSYS Multiphysics [20] tool as shown in Figure 4. The FEM unit cell model and the deformed shape of the unit cell are shown in Figure 4. The boundaries do not remain plane after load application, and shear stresses are uniform in the unit cell. The table on the far right side of Figure 4 compares the present results with Xia [18] demonstrating excellent agreement of shear strain, shear stress, and equivalent shear modulus.

4.2 Boundary Conditions for 3D Unit Cell

The next step was to define a finite element model of a square unit cell and repeated array in order to compare the behaviour under identical loadings and boundary conditions. The 3-D structural solid element, SOLID45, is used for the FEM analysis. The material properties of Silenka E-Glass 1200 tex and MY750 Epoxy are given in Table (1). The responses of the multi-cell array and the unit cell model were compared for different loading conditions with proper periodic boundary conditions. As an example, the comparison of the SQR multi-cell array and the SQR unit cell model under shear load is shown in Figure 5. It is clear that the stress distributions in the multi-cell model and the unit cell are identical. There is no boundary separation, which verifies the boundary conditions. The rest of the boundary conditions were verified in a similar manner.

Figure 4: 2D Unit Cell Shear stress (MPa) distribution and results comparison

Properties	E-glass Fiber	Properties	MY750 Epoxy
E_{11} (GPa)	74.0	E_m (GPa)	3.35
E_{22}, E_{33} (GPa)	74.0	ν_m (-)	0.35
G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	30.8		
ν_{12} (-)	0.2		

Table 1: Material Properties of Fiber and Matrix

Figure 5: Comparison of Shear Stress (N/m^2) distribution in Multi-Cell & SQR Unit Cell Model

4.3 UD Ply Stiffness Properties

To verify the homogenization technique, the stiffness properties were determined with the SQR and HEX unit cell first and compared with test data [22] as well as predictions from SROM and MROM. The same E-glass fibre and MY750 epoxy were used for this analysis. The stiffness properties were

calculated in the linear elastic region. The comparisons were made using a 60% fiber volume fraction. The predictions were compared with test data [22] and were found to be in good agreement, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Comparison of Stiffness Properties

4.4 Statistical Model Description and Monte Carlo Simulation

In this section, the Monte Carlo Simulation approach is coupled with a homogenization based stiffness calculation procedure to access the uncertainty of the stiffness properties of UD due to variation in the constituent's properties. This coupling is achieved in three steps: 1) generation of realizations according to the Latin Hypercube Sampling technique of random variables, i.e. the fiber and the matrix; 2) using the RUC and homogenization approach to simulate UD properties against each set of realizations; 3) post-processing the results to calculate statistical response and sensitivities of the output response parameters. Steps 1 and 2 were implemented in the finite element tool ANSYS PDS and ANSYS Multiphysics respectively by user defined subroutines. Step 3 is performed partially in ANSYS PDS and particularly in MATLAB. The generation of the realizations is based on a Gaussian distribution is used for the fiber and matrix property random variables. Note that an alternate choice of the distribution type would not modify the overall methodology. The details of the constituent random variables are given in the Table 2. The properties of the constituents (E-glass fiber and MY750 matrix) were taken from [22]. A 5% standard deviation is considered where data was missing for a particular quantity. The required number of Monte Carlo simulations is 400 according to [23].

The results of the probabilistic analysis after post-processing in MATLAB are given in Figures 7. The response parameters are presented as histograms along with the PDFs fit to the data; a Gaussian was found to be a good fit for the UD properties. The higher standard deviation in the stiffness property of the fiber is reflected in the UD longitudinal property response parameter. The probability that the UD longitudinal stiffness E_{11} is smaller than 35 GPa is 0.167 with a 95% confidence level. The lower stiffness of E-glass/epoxy composites will cause more deflection in the blade. Therefore, it is important to calculate this probability.

The evaluation of the probabilistic sensitivities is based on the correlation coefficients between all random input variables and a particular random output parameter. The sensitivity analysis was performed using the Spearman rank coefficient of correlation approach to investigate correlation between input design variables and output response parameters. The results of this analysis are shown in Figure 8. These correlations explain the strength of the relationship between the stochastic quantities and range from -1 to +1. A correlation of -1 describes perfect negative relation and +1 a perfect positive relation. A correlation close to 0 indicates no or weak relation. It can be clearly seen from Figure 8 that UD longitudinal stiffness $E_{1,Eq}$ has a strong relation with fiber longitudinal modulus. Likewise, $E_{2,Eq}$ has a strong positive relation (close to 1) with matrix modulus E_m . The shear properties of composites are also very important, particularly in wind turbine blade shear webs

[24]. The sensitivity analysis shows that the matrix shear modulus G_m correlates very highly with UD lamina shear modulus, i.e. $G_{12,Eq}, G_{13,Eq}, G_{23,Eq}$ but G_m has only a minor sensitivity to the UD lamina Poisson's ratio. This sensitivity analysis aids in improving the material according to design requirements as well as screening out unnecessary design variables for optimization purposes.

Material	Random Variable	ANSYS Symbols	units	Mean	Std dev
Fiber	Longitudinal modulus	E_11	GPa	74.00	18.50
	Transverse modulus	E_22	GPa	74.00	14.80
	Transverse modulus	E_33	GPa	74.00	14.80
	In-plane shear modulus	G_12	GPa	30.80	7.70
	Transverse shear modulus	G_13	GPa	30.80	6.16
	Transverse shear modulus	G_23	GPa	30.80	6.16
	Major Poisson's ratio	nu_12	-	0.20	0.01
	Minor Poisson's ratio	nu_13	-	0.23	0.01
Matrix	Elastic Modulus	E_mm	GPa	3.35	0.84
	Poisson's ratio	nu_mm	-	0.35	0.02
	Shear modulus	G_mm	GPa	1.24	0.25

Table 2: Input Random Variables for Calculation of UD Properties

The statistical interdependence between the output response parameters was also calculated by a Spearman rank order correlation coefficients approach. Figure 8 shows the sensitivity plot of the response parameters, i.e. UD stiffness properties. Evidently some properties are strongly correlated with others and some only in a weak manner. This is important information for further analysis of the wind turbine blade in ascertaining overall structural performance.

Figure 7: Histograms & PDFs of Output Parameter

Figure 8: Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficients

5 Application to a Wind Turbine Blade Section

A case study was carried out to highlight the implications of the micromechanics-based probabilistic analysis for realistic application to a composite wind turbine blade structure. The geometry and other specifications of the rotor blade considered in this research is based on the NREL 5MW baseline wind turbine described in [25]. A part of the blade is considered for simplicity of computation. The details of the blade wing box and the composite layup sequence are given in Figure 10. The investigated blade consists of three different types of E-glass/epoxy composites: unidirectional (UD) plies, BX $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$, and TX $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ]_s$. The UD and TX are used in the shell structure along with a PVC core. The BX and PVC core [26] is used in shear webs to provide shear resistance. The statistical moments and distribution type of UD properties used for wing box analysis were calculated from the probabilistic analysis on RUC as described in the previous section.

The finite element model of the wing box was generated in the ANSYS Multiphysics module. The wing box was modelled using the SHELL181 ANSYS element type [20]. Two types of loads were applied: flapwise and edgewise loads. These loads were calculated using an aeroelastic computer-aided engineering tool for horizontal axis wind turbines, FAST [27]. One is flapwise wise load (2.99×10^4 N) and other is edgewise load (7.50×10^4 N). The quasi-static analysis were performed according to IEC-DLC 6.1 load case [6].

Figure 11 illustrates the procedure used to calculate the probabilistic response of the wing box caused by uncertainties in the UD properties in a modular manner. These modules consist of: 1) selection of input design variables and description of their mean and standard deviation along with distribution type; 2) realization generation using efficient Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) approach; 3) user subroutine is used to calculate stiffness properties of UD with micro model and periodic boundary conditions (PBCs); 4) post processing of data performed once convergence criteria on mean values and standard deviations is met; 5) filters are applied with a threshold of 35% on the correlations given in Figure 8 to screen the unimportant design variables; 6) probabilistic finite element analysis were performed on the wing box with filtered correlation matrix and stochastic properties of UD. The results of step 6 were then post-processed to calculate the overall probabilistic response of the wing box. A summary of the stochastic response of the wing box deflection is shown in the Figure 12 with and without considering correlation and the fitted PDF on the right side of the figure. The PDF fit to the data is a Weibull distribution, even though the distributions of inputs were Gaussian. Several methods have been devised to estimate the Weibull parameters that will fit the particular data distribution; the Weibull parameters are given in the figure. The MCS applied in this work used 500 realizations for probabilistic analysis of the blade section, without the use of a MCS convergence criterion. As can be seen from the histogram on the left side and the fit PDF on the right side of Figure 12, the correlations have little effect on the maximum displacement of the wing box. However, inclusion of the correlation coefficients highlighted in detail the important factors on the deflection of

wing box, as shown in Figure 13 which shows the sensitivities on output response parameter with a 95% significance level. Based on these results, ignoring correlations suppressed the sensitivities of input variables on the response parameters. The consideration of correlations helps to screen some of the unimportant factors such as $E_{3,Eq}$, $E_{2,Eq}$, $\nu_{12,Eq}$, $\nu_{13,Eq}$ using a threshold of 20%. These parameters can therefore be treated as deterministic in the future reliability analysis. Overall, these analyses illustrate the capability of the coupled approach for structural robust analysis by indicating the variables to change in order to achieve a given reliability level.

Figure 9: Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient Matrix between Output Parameters

Figure 10: Blade Wing Box and Stacking Sequence

Figure 11: Flow chart for Probabilistic Analysis of Wing Box

Figure 12: Wing Box Deflection with and without Correlation

Figure 13: Wing Box Deflection Sensitivities with and without Correlation

6 CONCLUSION

This work aimed to develop a coupled approach for stiffness property prediction of composite materials used in wind turbine blades using advanced micromechanics and reliability-based methodologies. The homogenization approach was used with a unit cell to estimate composite material stiffness properties. The predicted results were compared with SRM and MROM along with the test data and found to be in good agreement with test data and MROM. The work was then extended to perform the probabilistic analysis with Monte Carlo Simulation to incorporate uncertainties in the constituent's properties. Latin Hypercube Sampling was employed to cover most of the input variable design space. From the probabilistic analysis, it was found that the equivalent properties of UD followed a Gaussian distribution. The Spearman Rank Order sensitivity analysis gave insights into important constituent properties and found that the modulus of fiber and matrix has more influence on composite properties. In addition, correlations were calculated between UD properties which were then used in blade analysis. From a practical point of view, the method was then applied to a 5MW wind turbine blade structural analysis. A section of the blade was considered for demonstration purposes. Two analyses were simulated with and without correlations between UD properties. There was no significant difference between PDFs but ignoring correlations suppressed the sensitivities of input variables on the response of wing box. In future work, the proposed probabilistic analysis can help determine constraints for use in structural optimization. The next step in this research is to expand the micromechanics based probabilistic analysis to estimate strength and fatigue life of composites using advanced probabilistic approach.

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